

Virtual modelling assisted stochastic size-dependent stability analysis of the perovskite solar cell

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Abstract

The perovskite solar cell (PSC), as a disruptive breakthrough within next-generation photovoltaic devices, has become one of the most burgeoning market challengers with intrinsic micro-scales in structural thickness. One of the main concerns for the PSC micro-composite during its operation is the structural stability due to ultra-thin characteristics [1-5]. In addition, uncertainties inherently exist in practical applications, and ignorance could yield disastrous micro-structural buckling failure [6]. Hence, this research presents the first work in performing the stochastic size-dependent stability analysis of the PSC micro-composite. A virtual modelling (VM) technique, namely the kernelized Extended Support Vector Regression (XSVR), is introduced to describe the underpinned relationships between the input uncertainties and stability performance mathematically, and to furnish sufficient statistical information. Besides, the virtual model is capable of providing accurate buckling failure forecasts under changing conditions with superior efficiencies, enabling the information update and inspiring the diagnosis-prognosis loop.

The architecture of the PSC micro-composite is illustrated in Figure 1 [7, 8]. The stability formulations are derived by incorporating the refined shear deformation theory, modified strain gradient theory, Hamilton's principle, and Galerkin method. Then, the buckling load is captured by solving the eigenvalue problem.

Figure 1. The PSC micro-composite on the Winkler-Pasternak elastic foundation and the architecture

Table 1. Validations of dimensionless critical buckling loads of micro-composite plates with size effects

a/h	$h/l(l_0=l_1=l_2=l)$	Present	[9]	[10]
5	1	265.4077	264.6544	265.4077

5	2	78.5650	78.3974	78.5650
10	5	29.7615	29.7597	29.7615
10	10	21.3765	21.3761	21.3765

Table 2. Statistical information of random variables in the PSC micro-composite properties

Random variables	Distribution	Mean	STD
E_{Au}	Lognormal [11]	78[GPa]	3.9[GPa]
$E_{Spiro-MeOTAD}$	Lognormal [11]	15[GPa]	0.75[GPa]
$\nu_{Perovskite}$	Beta [12]	0.33	0.0065
$E_{Perovskite}$	Normal [13]	17.8 [GPa]	0.534 [GPa]
$E_{Mesoporous}$	Lognormal [11, 14]	210.44 [GPa]	10.522 [GPa]
ρ_{TiO_2}	Normal [13]	$4.23[10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3]$	$0.423[10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3]$
ρ_{FTO}	Normal [13]	$6.85[10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3]$	$0.2055[10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3]$

Figure 2. The convergence study of R^2 of predicted critical buckling loads of the PSC micro-composite

A verification of the presented size-dependent stability analysis (SDSA) has been implemented in Table 1. In stochastic analysis, 7 uncertainties have been considered and reported in Table 2. The brute-force Monte Carlo simulation (MCS) with 100000 iterations is implemented as the benchmark. A convergence study of the R-square (R^2) of critical buckling loads is performed in Figure 2. Then, the statistical information, PDF, CDF,

and relative error are exhibited in Figures 3-5. The VM (XSVR) has been compared against the support vector regression (SVR), Neural Network (NN), and Kriging, which demonstrates the advantages of the presented VM technique. Besides, the computational costs of the MCS and VM are 588.2min and 3.857min, respectively, which exhibit the appealing efficiency of the developed VM strategy. Moreover, three arbitrary new sets of the PSC micro-composite properties are further examined beyond the original variation range. The results in Table 4 demonstrate the feasibility, exactness, and efficiency of the proposed VM tactic with updated information and under varying system conditions, facilitating the prognostic feature, micro-composite health status assessment, and structural decision-making in the physical reality.

Figure 3. The estimated PDF of buckling loads

Figure 4. The estimated CDF of buckling loads

Figure 5. The relative error (RE) of the CDF and Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) statistic against MCS

Table 3. New input data sets of the PSC micro-composite properties

Properties	Set1	Set2	Set3
E_{Au}	90.08[GPa]	71.01[GPa]	65.24[GPa]
$E_{Spiro-MeOTAD}$	17.44[GPa]	13.92[GPa]	13.39[GPa]
$\nu_{Perovskite}$	0.3405	0.3171	0.3420
$E_{Perovskite}$	19.19[GPa]	16.67[GPa]	19.22[GPa]
$E_{Mesoporous}$	195.7[GPa]	230.2[GPa]	188.8[GPa]
ρ_{TiO_2}	4.563[10^3 kg/m ³]	3.419[10^3 kg/m ³]	3.353[10^3 kg/m ³]
ρ_{FTO}	7.419[10^3 kg/m ³]	6.298[10^3 kg/m ³]	7.371[10^3 kg/m ³]

Table 4. Predicted critical buckling loads for new property input sets

Model comparison	Set1	Set2	Set3
Virtual model[Pa]	8.4125 $\times 10^6$	8.4858 $\times 10^6$	8.3627 $\times 10^6$
Size-dependent stability analysis[Pa]	8.4129 $\times 10^6$	8.4797 $\times 10^6$	8.3565 $\times 10^6$
Relative error[%]	4.755 $\times 10^{-2}$	7.194 $\times 10^{-2}$	7.419 $\times 10^{-2}$
VM time[s]	0.1094	7.780 $\times 10^{-2}$	0.1069
SDSA time[s]	0.5748	0.3529	0.3006

Key words: virtual model; stochastic size-dependent stability analysis; perovskite solar cell

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